

EXPORT SPECIALIZATION OF BANGLADESH'S READYMADE GARMENTS INDUSTRY IN THE NORTH AMERICAN MARKET

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Abstract:

This paper attempts to investigate the export specialization of Bangladesh readymade garments industry among leading readymade garments exporting nations in the North American market. An export specialization (ES) index is employed to evaluate the export specialization of the top 5 competitors in the North American market during the 2012-2016 period. Export specialization was calculated for 34 product categories of four digits level Harmonized System (HS) product group 61 and 62. The mean and standard deviation were also calculated to examine the degree of change in the readymade garments export specialization of Bangladesh in the North American market for the study period. The analyzed results demonstrate the status of export specialization of selected competitors where Bangladesh exposed the highest export specialization over their competitors in the North American market for 27 product groups out of 34. However, ES of Bangladesh is not steady, in fact, unsteady ES was observed for 10 product groups, and in addition to that, ES of the 8 product groups shows downtrend. Established trade theories regarding export specialization remain a useful but limited guide to understand the dynamic of export specialization for the given market. Policy recommendation in the context of the changing global business environment and geopolitical transformation were discussed and future implications of the research direction were recommended.

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Keywords: readymade garments, export specialization, North American market, Bangladesh

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1. Introduction

Bangladesh is the second largest ready-made garment exporter in the world, has emerged as a key player since 1978. Textiles & Clothing account for about 85% of total export of Bangladesh. Out of which 86% comes from the apparel sector which covers the major products of knit & woven shirts, blouses, trousers, skirts, shorts, sweaters, sportswear & many more casual & fashion items (Hasan, Mia, Rahman, Ullah, & Ullah, 2016). Bangladesh is a growing economy which is mainly powered by the readymade garments (RMG) industry has promoted the country in the world through the motto 'Made in Bangladesh'. The RMG industry has become the main lifelines of Bangladesh economy, sharing a major part of the country's export earnings (Islam, Rakib, & Adnan, 2016). Textile & clothes, raw jute, and its derived products, leather, fish and frozen seafood are the main export products of Bangladesh (Comtrade, 2018). According to the newly released World Trade Statistical Review 2018 by the World Trade Organization (WTO), the current dollar value of world textiles and apparel exports totaled \$296.1bn and \$454.5bn respectively in 2017, increased by 4.2% and 2.8% from a year earlier (Organization, 2018). Asia recorded the highest increase in trade volume with the growth of 8.1%.

Bangladesh's main export partners are the European Union, North America and Emerging countries in Asia, South America and Africa (Comtrade, 2018). Bangladesh relies heavily on the United States, European Union, and Canada for exporting clothing. In 2017, North American Market was accounted for 18% of total export by Bangladesh (Appendix 3) and the majority of the exported item to North American Market were readymade garments. There are 34 products under the four digits level Harmonized System (HS) product group 61 and 62 as readymade garments products which are being exported to the major export partners of Bangladesh. North American Market accounts for 10.7% of total export for the product group under Harmonized System (HS) 61, and 25% for the product group under Harmonized System (HS) 62 (Appendix 4,5). In 2017, Bangladesh exported goods worth US \$ 1.1 billion to Canada, more than 95 percent of which was readymade garment item. The total two-way trade between the two countries was worth the US \$ 1.87 billion in 2017. Of the total export to Canada from Bangladesh, the majority of products are clothing items, as this North American country has been giving duty-free trade benefit for all goods to Bangladesh since 2004.

Bangladesh is facing stringent competition from Vietnam, India, Indonesia, and China in the North American market. Thus, a competitive firm or industry or country have the ability to satisfy the consumers with a product of the right price, right quality, right packaging, etc. (Ilyas, Mukhtar, & Javed, 2009). A large or growing market share is the outcome of successful competition and one of the measures focusing on market share is the revealed comparative advantage (RCA) proposed by Balassa (1965). According to this indicator, a country has a comparative advantage in a particular product if its exports of the product, relative to world exports of the product, are larger than the country's market share in total exports. Therefore, comparative advantages

and the export specialization is very important for Bangladesh to survive the extensive competition.

Thus, this study aims to analyze the export specialization of Bangladesh readymade garments in the North American market. All 34 product categories of four digits level Harmonized System (HS) product group 61 and 62 were analyzed individually to determine export specialization of Bangladesh readymade garments in North American Market. In this context, the Balassa index (1965) was used to measure the export specialization at Harmonized System HS 4-digits levels. Balassa developed the 'Revealed Comparative Advantage' (RCA) index concept in order to analyses international trade (Balassa, 1965, 1977). The RCA index identifies the success in exporting of a country compared to the world or a group of countries (Siggel, 2006).

This study aims to provide a picture relative position of readymade garments of Bangladesh in the North American markets where few types of research have been conducted before that illustrates the value of this research.

However, the objectives of this research are as following;

- 1) To explore the overall status of the export specialization of Bangladesh in the North American Market.
- 2) To investigate the challenges faced by Bangladesh's readymade garments industry in the North American Market.
- 3) To discover the unexploited potentiality of Bangladesh's readymade garments industry in the North American Market.
- 4) To advise a sustainable growth of readymade garments industry of Bangladesh in North American Market.

2. Literature Review

Basically, export competitiveness is a supporting conception of international competitiveness. It implies better export performance in terms of price and quality as compared to other nations in export markets while maintaining economic growth and employment (Bruneckiene & Paltanaviciene, 2012; Ketels, 2010; Wagner, 2007). Most of the researches show that the more developed a country is the more specialized is the structure of international trade and, therefore, a larger part of trade within a branch dominates in the total scope of international trade (Tiits & Juriado, 2006, McAleese, 2004 etc.).

(Balassa, 1977) states that comparative advantage is revealed by observing trade patterns and investigating the shares of exports of a particular commodity in relation to total world exports. Amongst all the competitive indices, Balassa RCA became widely accepted method in export specialization and comparative advantages of a country with reference to other countries (Balassa, 1965, 1977; Fertö & Hubbard, 2003; Vollrath, 1991).

Sheetal and Kumar (2015), analyzed the export competitiveness of India through various trade indices; RCA, RMA, RCA2, RSCA, and the export specialization index

(Modified RCA) from the period 2001-2013 and found that export competitiveness is not consistent across the years and not uniform across all product categories (Kumar, 2015). Furthermore, in their study, major structural changes in export specialization patterns have been observed in Asian, North American and European markets over the years (Kumar, 2015).

Dalia Bernatonyte (2009) investigated the extent of intra-industry trade between Lithuania and the European Union and its role in export specialization by using The Grubel-Lloyd index, marginal intra-industry trade index, the export specialization index and Nomenclature of commodities (CN) (Bernatonyte, 2009).

A Mahmood (2000) did an in-depth analysis of shifting export specialization at the SITC 3-digit product category level and links this analysis to Malaysian export potential by using the revealed comparative advantage framework to find the extent of export competition between Malaysia and other ASEAN economies (Mahmood, 2000). Rehner et al. (2014) analyzed how the degree of export specialization among Chile's regions is linked to regional GDP growth and to regional export growth (Rehner, Baeza, & Barton, 2014). They measured export specialization and its development over time by using the Herfindahl–Hirschmann Index (HHI) (Gordo, Gil, & Pérez, 2003).

However, very few researches have been conducted on the export specialization of Bangladesh's readymade garments industry in the North American Market, which motivated this research to be conducted.

3. Research Method

There are different methods to measure export competitiveness, and different researchers actually used the different index but Balassa RCA became widely accepted method in export specialization and comparative advantages of a country with reference to other countries (Balassa, 1965, 1977; Fertö & Hubbard, 2003; Vollrath, 1991). In this paper, Balassa's (1965) "revealed comparative advantage" (RCA) approach have been used for analyzing export specialization. Balassa's measure of relative export performance by country and industry/commodity is defined as a country's share of world exports of a commodity divided by its share of total world exports. The index for the country "i" and commodity "j" is calculated as follows:

$$ES_{ij} = X_{ij} \div X_i / X_{wj} \div X_w$$

Where:

X_{ij} = 'i' the country's export of commodity j.

X_{wj} = world exports of commodity j.

X_i = total exports of country i.

X_w = total world exports.

Export specialization was calculated for all 34 product categories of four digits level Harmonized System (HS) ((HS)) product group 61 and 62 (see appendix 1) with

the help of Balassa's index for top exporters respectively Bangladesh, Cambodia, China, India, and Vietnam in North American market (United States of America and Canada). For calculation, export data has been obtained from the ITC Trade Map and the United Nations Commodity Trade Database (COMTRADE) and 6 years (2012-2016) data has been calculated for using Microsoft Excel program (Organization, 2018; WITS, 2018). The result has been presented through the table and different figures/graphs to show the standing of export specialization of Bangladesh's readymade garments products in North American along with other four top exporters respectively Vietnam, China, Indonesia, and India.

4. Results and Discussion

The analysis has been done for 34 product categories of four digits level Harmonized System (HS) product group 61 and 62 which are readymade garments products. Export specialization and their standing for individual readymade garments product have been explained through graphs presented below.

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The analyzed result (Figure 1) shows tremendous ups and down in export specialization for the products under HS code 6101 (Men's overcoats, capes, etc.) for Bangladesh in North American Market in the period 2012-2016. Vietnam had the most export competitiveness followed by Indonesia and Bangladesh in 2012 but in 2014 Bangladesh took over Vietnam and export competitiveness fall in 2015 and rise again in 2016 in the North American Market. A similar trend (Figure 2) can be seen for the products under HS code 6102 (Women's overcoat, cape, etc.).

Bangladesh has export specialization for both HS6103 (Men's suits, jackets, trousers etc.) (Figure 3) and HS6104 (Women's suits, dresses, skirt etc.) (Figure 4) products throughout the years. For the products, HS6103 Bangladesh is at way better position than other competitors but comparative advantage decreased a little bit in the year 2016. On the other hand, for the products HS6104 the export comparative advantage increased over the years and reached its peak in the year 2016.

Result shows Bangladesh has significant export specialization for the products group HS6105 (Men's shirts, knitted or crocheted, etc.) (Figure 5), HS6106 (Women's blouses & shirts, etc.) (Figure 6), HS6107 (Men's underpants, pajamas, etc.) (Figure 7), and HS6108 (Women's slips, panties etc.) (Figure 8) in the North American Market. Bangladesh's export specialization is way higher than its competitors for the products group HS6109 (T-shirts, singlets, etc.) (Figure 9) and HS6110 (Jerseys, pullovers, cardigans, etc.) (Figure 10). However, Figure 9 shows a downtrend in the export specialization of Bangladesh in the North American market.

Figure 11 and Figure 12 shows interesting ups and down in export specialization for the products under HS6111 (Babies' garments, knitted, etc.) and HS6112 (Tracksuits, and swimwear, etc.). But in the both category Bangladesh kept its export specialization and the value is uprising.

Figure 13 shows that Bangladesh had significant export specialization for the products group HS6113 (Garment, knitted fabric, etc.) in the year 2012, but over the years the ES score decreased and reached to the lowest point where Bangladesh and Vietnam's export competitiveness become equal. Bangladesh again gains the specialization over competitors in the year 2015. Figure 14 shows that Vietnam is in the leading position for the product group HS6114 (Garments, knitted lines etc.) in the year 2012-13, but Bangladesh took over Vietnam and gain significant export competitiveness in the year 2014 and fall behind Vietnam, India, and China in 2015 then again reached to the top in 2016.

China is having the significant export specialization (Figure 15) in North American Market for the products HS6115 (Pantyhose, tights, stockings etc.), and other competitors like Bangladesh, Vietnam, Indonesia, and India are falling far behind compare to China in that market. China is leading the market (Figure 16) in the North American Market for the products HS6116 (Gloves, mittens, and mitts, etc.) but the other competitors Bangladesh, Vietnam, Indonesia, and India are not very far behind than China. The position of China is at the top followed by Vietnam, Bangladesh, Indonesia, and India for the mentioned product group. China is leading (Figure 17) the market for the product group of HS6117 (Clothing access news, knitted, etc.) as well. Bangladesh had a jump in the year 2014, and fall again in 2015 then again competitiveness upraised a bit in 2016 but still were behind China.

Export specialization and their standing for individual readymade garments product 62 Articles of apparel, accessories, not knit or crochet are explained through graphs presented below

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Bangladesh having significant export specialization in the North American market over their competitors for the products groups of HS6201 (Men's overcoats, capes, etc) (Figure 18), HS6203 (Men's suits, jackets, trousers etc) (Figure 20), HS6204 (Women's suits, jackets, skirts etc) (Figure 21), HS6205 (Men's shirts) (Figure 22), HS6206 (Women's blouses & shirts) (Figure 23), HS6207 (Men's singlets, pyjamas, etc) (Figure 24), HS6208 (Women's singlets, pyjamas, etc) (Figure 25), HS6209 (Babies' garments accessories) (Figure 26), HS6210 (Garment made up fabric heading) (Figure 27), and HS6212 (Brassieres, girdles, corsets, etc) (Figure 29).

Figure 19 shows that in the year 2012-2013, Vietnam had the highest export specialization for the product group HS6202 (Women's overcoats, capes, etc) but Bangladesh took over Vietnam in 2014 and again Vietnam took over Bangladesh 2015 and in 2016 Bangladesh had more export specialization in mentioned product group.

For the product group HS6211 (Track suits, ski suits, and swimwear) (Figure 28), there were ups and downs in the export specialization for Bangladesh but at the end, Bangladesh was leading the North American Market.

India and China have the most export specialization for the product group HS6214 (Shawls, scarves, mantillas, etc.) (Figure 31), in North American Market. On the other hand, Bangladesh, Vietnam, and Indonesia have almost no competitiveness for the above-mentioned products.

China was at the top with highest export specialization for the products group HS6215 (Ties, bow ties, and cravats) (Figure 32) in the period 2012-2015 but surprisingly in 2016, all the analyzed countries' (China, India, Indonesia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam) have no export competitiveness. For the product group HS6216 (Gloves, mittens, and mitts) Vietnam is most competitive in the North American Market.

Table 1: Top two countries in terms of export specialization score in North American Market for all products under HS61, and HS 62

HS Code	Export Specialization		HS Code	Export Specialization	
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD
HS 6101	Bangladesh	18.4	HS 6201	Bangladesh	15.38
	Vietnam	14.4		Vietnam	10.42
HS 6102	Bangladesh	20.8	HS 6202	Bangladesh	8.78
	Vietnam	8		Vietnam	7.94
HS 6103	Bangladesh	17.4	HS 6203	Bangladesh	69.14
	China	4.92		Vietnam	5.9
HS 6104	Bangladesh	14.14	HS 6204	Bangladesh	30.3
	Vietnam	5.08		Vietnam	5.34
HS 6105	Bangladesh	53.22	HS 6205	Bangladesh	82.84
	Vietnam	7.52		Vietnam	6.08
HS 6106	Bangladesh	22.72	HS 6206	Bangladesh	23.44
	Vietnam	6.28		India	7.08
HS 6107	Bangladesh	31.78	HS 6207	Bangladesh	23.36
	Vietnam	7.9		Vietnam	5.4
HS 6108	Bangladesh	25.3	HS 6208	Bangladesh	13.7
	China	3.56		India	5.3
HS 6109	Bangladesh	73.24	HS 6209	Bangladesh	42.8
	Vietnam	4.22		India	6.6
HS 6110	Bangladesh	38.3	HS 6210	Bangladesh	13.32
	Vietnam	5.66		Vietnam	6.1
HS 6111	Bangladesh	25.08	HS 6211	Bangladesh	6.66
	India	6.54		Vietnam	5.2
HS 6112	Bangladesh	7.16	HS 6212	Bangladesh	12.92
	Vietnam	4.1		Indonesia	3.3
HS 6113	Bangladesh	5	HS 6213	N/A	
	Vietnam	2.8		N/A	
HS 6114	Bangladesh	9.18	HS 6214	India	10.28
	Vietnam	7.76		China	3.42
HS 6115	China	3.64	HS 6215	China	1.6
	Indonesia	1.06		Vietnam	.6
HS 6116	China	4.4	HS 6216	Vietnam	7.4
	Vietnam	2.9		Indonesia	2.6
HS 6117	China	3.7	HS 6217	Bangladesh	9.6
	India	1.2		China	1.2

Table 1 shows the export specialization (ES) of top two countries in North American market for all 34 products under HS 61, and HS 62. The mean value shows that Bangladesh is at the top for most (27/34) of the above-mentioned products in terms of export specialization but the scores are different. China is at the top for 4 products (HS 6115, HS 6215, HS 6116, and HS 6117) categories. Vietnam and India both having highest export specialization for one category each, HS 6216 and HS 6213 respectively. There are two things for Bangladesh to concern about in North American Market. First one is the stability of export specialization, as STDEV shows that even though Bangladesh is at the top for 27 out of 34 product categories but for most of the

categories the standard deviation is high which indicates the export specialization is not steady in North American market. Another concern is that, out of 27 product categories Bangladesh having the Export specialization, 19 of them Vietnam, 3 of them China, 4 of them India, and 1 of them Indonesia are the immediate competitors. So, Vietnam could be a big concern for Bangladesh as in 8 categories (HS6103, HS6105, HS6109, HS6203, HS6204, HS6205, HS6207, and HS6217) Bangladesh's ES score is a decreasing trend (See figure. 3, 5, 9, 20, 21, 22, 24, and 34).

Table 2: Situation of Export Specialization of Bangladesh's readymade garments industry in North American Market

Export competitiveness	Products
Very High ($ES \geq 50$) and Steady ($STDEV < 10$)	HS 6105, HS 6205
Very High ($ES \geq 50$) but not Steady ($STDEV > 10$)	HS 6109, HS 6203
High ($30 \leq ES < 50$) and Steady ($STDEV < 8$)	HS 6110, HS 6204, HS 6107
High ($30 \leq ES < 50$) but not Steady ($STDEV > 8$)	HS 6209
Moderate ($10 \leq ES < 30$) and Steady ($STDEV < 5$)	HS 6103, HS 6108, HS 6201, HS 6206, HS 6207, HS 6208, HS 6212,
Moderate ($10 \leq ES < 30$) but not Steady ($STDEV > 5$)	HS 6101, HS 6102, HS 6104, HS 6106, HS 6111, HS 6210,
Low ($ES < 10$)	HS 6112, HS 6113, HS 6114, HS 6202, HS 6211, HS 6217

Out of 34 products categories 27 of them Bangladesh, 4 (HS 6115, HS 6116, HS 6117, HS 6215) of them China, 1 (HS 6214) of them India, and 1 (HS 6216) of them Vietnam is having highest export specialization. 27 products categories which Bangladesh is leading are analyzed in 7 categories to better understand the situation of export specialization of Bangladesh in North American Market. Bangladesh is having very high ES score for (HS 6105, HS 6205), high ES score for (HS 6110, HS 6204, HS 6107) and the growth over the year is steady. Bangladesh is having very high ES score products categories (HS 6109, HS 6203), and high ES score for (HS 6209) as well but standard deviation is high which indicates the growth of export competitiveness is not steady over last 6 years. Products groups of (HS 6103, HS 6108, HS 6201, HS 6206, HS 6207, HS 6208, and HS 6212) have moderate ES score and the growth is steady as well but products group of (HS 6101, HS 6102, HS 6104, HS 6106, HS 6111, and HS 6210) have the moderate ES score however the growth is not stable. Some products categories (HS 6112, HS 6113, HS 6114, HS 6202, HS 6211, and HS 6217) Bangladesh at the top but the score is not comparatively low.

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This paper examines the current status & trend of export specialization of Bangladesh's readymade garments industry in the North American Market during the study period. Export specialization (ES) indices were calculated for HS 61 and HS 62 clothing products at the HS four-digit level for the period from 2012 to 2016. Mean and standard deviation were also calculated to examine the degree of change in the readymade garments export specialization of Bangladesh in the North American market for the study period.

The results revealed that out of 34 products categories under HS 61 (articles of apparel and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted) & HS 62 (articles of apparel and clothing accessories, not knitted or crocheted), 27 of them Bangladesh has highest export specialization in North American market. However, ES of Bangladesh is not steady, in fact, unsteady ES was observed for 10 product groups, and in addition to that ES of the 8 product groups' shows downtrend, 7 of them Bangladesh have very low or no export specialization.

The result pointed out that even though Bangladesh's readymade garments is leading in North American market their position is not steady and Vietnam is their main competitors in that market as out of 27 product categories Bangladesh having the superior export specialization, 19 of them Vietnam is their immediate competitor. Vietnam could grab a larger market share of readymade garments in the North American market if Bangladesh fails to keep or upraise its export specialization factors.

Significant government policy changes to reduce political instability, transaction cost, skilled labor development, and upgradation of rail, road, and port infrastructure needs to be undertaken immediately to stay competitive in the readymade garments industry.

6. Study Limitations and Implication for Future Research

There is an intense amount of empirical and theoretical literature on RCA, however not enough empirical literature found on the topic export specialization, especially on Bangladesh's Readymade Garments Industry. Therefore, this study was limited by inadequate literature. 5 years data was analyzed, so the findings may not represent better insights.

This study is a vital step towards findings export specialization of Bangladesh's readymade garments industry in the North American market as not enough studies found on this topic.

However, further research could be conducted on export specialization and diversification of Bangladesh readymade garments in the European market as European Market is one of the biggest export destinations for Bangladesh readymade garments. Moreover, the inclusion of a more complex range of variables is necessary to obtain a fuller understanding of export specialization among the competitors.

Appendix 1: Harmonized System (HS) code and product label

HS Code	Product Label	HS Code	Product Label
HS 6101	Men's or boys' overcoats, carcoats, capes, cloaks, anoraks, ski jacket etc.	HS 6201	Men's or boys' overcoats, carcoats, capes, cloaks, anoraks, ski jackets etc.
HS 6102	Women's or girls' overcoats, carcoats, capes, cloaks etc.	HS 6202	Women's or girls' overcoats, carcoats, capes, cloaks, anoraks etc.
HS 6103	Men's or boys' suits, ensembles, jackets, blazers, trousers, etc.	HS 6203	Men's or boys' suits, ensembles, jackets, blazers, trousers, bib etc.
HS 6104	Women's or girls' suits, ensembles, jackets, blazers, dresses, skirts etc.	HS 6204	Women's or girls' suits, ensembles, jackets, blazers, dresses, divided skirts.
HS 6105	Men's or boys' shirts, knitted or crocheted etc.	HS 6205	Men's or boys' shirts (excluding knitted or crocheted, nightshirts).
HS 6106	Women's or girls' blouses, shirts and shirt-blouses, knitted etc.	HS 6206	Women's or girls' blouses, shirts and shirt-blouses.
HS 6107	Men's or boys' underpants, briefs, nightshirts, pajamas, bathrobes etc.	HS 6207	Men's or boys' singlet's and other vests, underpants, briefs, nightshirts.
HS 6108	Women's or girls' slips, petticoats, briefs, panties, nightdresses, etc.	HS 6208	Women's or girls' singlets and other vests, slips, petticoats, briefs.
HS 6109	T-shirts, singlets and other vests, knitted or crocheted	HS 6209	Babies' garments and clothing accessories of textile materials.
HS 6110	Jerseys, pullovers, cardigans, waistcoats and similar, knitted etc.	HS 6210	Garments made up of felt or nonwovens, coated.
HS 6111	Babies' garments and clothing accessories, knitted etc.	HS 6211	Tracksuits, ski suits, swimwear, and other garments.
HS 6112	Track-suits, ski-suits, and swimwear, knitted or crocheted	HS 6212	Brassieres, girdles, corsets, braces, suspenders, garters.
HS 6113	Garments, knitted or crocheted, rubberized or impregnated.	HS 6213	Handkerchiefs, of which no side exceeds 60 cm
HS 6114	Special garments for professional, sporting or other purposes.	HS 6214	Shawls, scarves, mufflers, mantillas, veils and similar articles.
HS 6115	Pantyhose, tights, stockings, socks and other hosiery, incl.	HS 6215	Ties, bow ties, and cravats of textile materials
HS 6116	Gloves, mittens, and mitts, knitted or crocheted (excluding for babies)	HS 6216	Gloves, mittens, and mitts, of all types of textile materials.
HS 6117	Made-up clothing accessories knitted or crocheted; knitted.	HS 6217	Made-up clothing accessories and parts of garments or clothing accessories.

Appendix 2: Top Import Partners of North American Market in Readymade Garments Industry in 2017

Source: ITC Trade Map, compiled by the Authors in January 2019

Appendix 3: List of importing markets for the all products exported by Bangladesh in 2017

Source: ITC Trade Map, compiled by the Authors in January 2019

Appendix 4: List of importing markets for (61) Articles of apparel and clothing accessories product exported by Bangladesh in 2017

Source: ITC Trade Map, compiled by the Authors in January 2019

Appendix 5: List of importing markets for (62) Articles of apparel and clothing accessories product exported by Bangladesh in 2017

Source: ITC Trade Map, compiled by the Authors in January 2019

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IN THE NORTH AMERICAN MARKET

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